

Overstimulation vs Understimulation: A Search Trend Analysis

Akachi IHEME, Ashley Hodge

Introduction:

Overstimulation happens when the brain receives more input than it can efficiently process, often leading to stress and anxiety. It's commonly discussed in relation to screen time, especially in children. On the other hand, understimulation- a lack of sensory or mental engagement- gets far less attention, even though it also affects mental health. This study uses Google Trends to compare search interest in overstimulation to understimulation, and to highlight the need for more awareness of both.

Objectives:

Our aim is to compare American search interest in overstimulation and understimulation in health contexts over the past 5 years. This study will help bring more awareness to both these extremes of neurodivergence.

Methods:

To compare search popularity, I generated an *interest over time* chart by inputting the following search terms into the Google Trends Analysis search bar: *overstimulation*, and *low stimulation*. Thereafter, I specified the search category to *Health* to maintain focus and set the time range to generate data from the past 5 years. I then downloaded the *interest over time* chart and exported it to Microsoft Excel for analysis.

Results:

From July 2020 to July 2025, the mean value of relative American search interest in *overstimulation* was 57.7% of the maximum interest in the dataset (SD = 16.7). In contrast, *low stimulation* had a mean interest of 15.3% (SD = 13.1). For each individual year from 2020-2025, *overstimulation* had its highest mean interest in 2025 (mean = 71.4%, SD = 10.1), and its lowest in 2020 (mean = 29.2%, SD = 5.4). Meanwhile, *low stimulation* had its highest mean interest in 2025 (mean = 37.6%, SD = 7.49), and its lowest in 2020 (mean = 3.52%, SD = 5.7).

Discussion:

Public interest in overstimulation far exceeds that of understimulation in the U.S. While Google search data alone is not conclusive, it shows significant patterns in public awareness. The consistent attention to overstimulation points to increasing public sensitivity around sensory overload. Scientists could use these insights to increase awareness of both these extremes of neurodivergence, especially to guide parents and guardians toward better understanding sensory-related behaviors in children.

References:

Gottschalk, L. A., Haer, J. L., & Bates, D. E. (1972). Effect of sensory overload on psychological state: Changes in social alienation–personal disorganization and cognitive–intellectual impairment. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 27(4), 451–457. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.1972.01750280019004>

Finnigan, K. A. (2024). Sensory responsive environments: A qualitative study on perceived relationships between outdoor built environments and sensory sensitivities. *Land*, 13(5), 636. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land13050636>

Merchán-Bon, V., Delgado-Rincón, E., Pérez-Marfil, M. N., & Páez-Gallego, J. (2024). Moderator effect of overstimulation on quality of life and coping in highly sensitive people. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-024-06507-2>